

Job Hiring

April 28, 2026

1 Description

TechForYou, a leading technology firm, is hiring a software engineer based on candidates' likelihood of success, favoring those with higher potential.

1) **TechForYou relies on employees to assess an applicant's quality.**

- a) Imagine you are an applicant of TechForYou. How acceptable do you find it when an employee assesses the quality?
 - i) completely unacceptable
 - ii) somewhat unacceptable
 - iii) neutral
 - iv) somewhat acceptable
 - v) completely acceptable
- b) Please describe a situation where using employees would be beneficial for assessing the quality.
- c) Please describe a situation where using employees would be harmful for assessing the quality

RecruitTalent, a recruitment firm, collects resumes (including their technical skills, academic qualifications, experience, and portfolios) from applicants with criminal backgrounds.

RecruitTalent uses the collected data to develop an Artificial Intelligence (AI) to predict whether an applicant will succeed at the job.

2) **Instead of employees, the TechForYou now relies on RecruitTalent's AI to assess an applicant's quality.**

- a) Imagine you are an applicant of TechForYou. How acceptable do you find it when an AI assesses the quality?
 - i) completely unacceptable
 - ii) somewhat unacceptable
 - iii) neutral
 - iv) somewhat acceptable

v) completely acceptable

- Please describe a situation where using the AI would be beneficial for assessing the quality.
- Please describe a situation where using the AI would be harmful for assessing the quality.

3) **Consider that TechForYou relies on RecruitTalent’s AI to assess an applicant’s quality and evaluate their chance of being hired. RecruitTalent identified an issue with its AI that employees could exploit the AI to disadvantage blue-eyed applicants by giving them a lower chances of being hired, even though these applicants have a high potential. To address this, RecruitTalent modifies the AI to mitigate the issue.**

- Please describe how this ‘AI modification’ could be beneficial for everyone.

Modifying the AI has some side effects, which are described as different scenarios in parts (a), (b), (c), and (d). Please indicate your preference for the following scenarios:

a) **A side effect of modifying the AI is that it incorrectly predicts lower chances of being hired for high potential applicants. It is impossible to completely protect the AI manipulation by the employee and still provide correct chance of being hired for high potential applicants. In this scenario, if you were an applicant, which option would you suggest for RecruitTalent to choose?**

- i) The AI is not difficult to manipulate, and it provides highly correct chance of being hired.
- ii) The AI is moderately difficult to manipulate, and it provides slightly incorrect chance of being hired.
- iii) The AI is slightly difficult to manipulate, and it provides moderately incorrect chance of being hired.
- iv) The AI is highly difficult to manipulate, and it provides highly incorrect chance of being hired.

- Give an example of potential issues if RecruitTalent chooses a different approach than your suggestion.

b) **A side effect of modifying the AI is that TechForYou can learn whether an applicant has a criminal background by identifying if they were part of RecruitTalent’s data. It is impossible to completely protect the AI from manipulation and still prevent TechForYou from identifying applicants has a criminal background. In this scenario, if you were an applicant, which option would you suggest for RecruitTalent to choose?**

- i) The AI is not difficult to manipulate, and it has no chance to reveal whether the an applicant has a criminal background.
 - ii) The AI is moderately difficult to manipulate, and it has a slight chance to reveal whether the an applicant has a criminal background.
 - iii) The AI is slightly difficult to manipulate, and it has a moderate chance to reveal whether the an applicant has a criminal background.
 - iv) The AI is highly difficult to manipulate, and it has a high chance to reveal whether the an applicant has a criminal background.
 - Give an example of potential issues if RecruitTalent chooses a different approach than your suggestion.
- c) **The above modification of the AI has made it possible for TechForYou to determine the number of women in RecruitTalent’s collected data. It is impossible to completely protect the AI from manipulation and protect information about the number of women. In this scenario, if you were an applicant, which option would you suggest for RecruitTalent to choose?**
- i) The AI is not difficult to manipulate, and it has no chance to reveal the number of women in the data.
 - ii) The AI is moderately difficult to manipulate, and it has a slight chance to reveal the number of women in the data.
 - iii) The AI is slightly difficult to manipulate, and it has a moderate chance to reveal the number of women in the data.
 - iv) The AI is highly difficult to manipulate, and it has a high chance to reveal the number of women in the data.
 - Give an example of potential issues if RecruitTalent chooses a different approach than your suggestion.
- d) **A side effect of modifying the AI is that TechForYou’s employees can easily learn the information of the participants that RecruitTalent used to build the AI. It is impossible to completely protect the AI from manipulation while preventing information learning. In this scenario, if you were an applicant, which option would you suggest for RecruitTalent to choose?**
- i) The AI is not difficult to manipulate, and there is no chance to learn the information used to build the AI.
 - ii) The AI is moderately difficult to manipulate, and there is a slight chance to learn the information used to build the AI.
 - iii) The AI is slightly difficult to manipulate, and there is a moderate chance to learn the information used to build the AI.

- iv) The AI is highly difficult to manipulate, and there is a high chance to learn the information used to build the AI.
 - Give an example of potential issues if RecruitTalent chooses a different approach than your suggestion.

2 Demographic Information

- 1) What is your gender?
 - Man | Woman | Non-Binary | Prefer not to answer | Self-describe [text input]
- 2) Do you identify as being part of any minority groups?
 - Yes | No | Prefer not to answer
- 3) What age group do you belong to?
 - 18-25 | 26-35 | 36-45 | 46-55 | 56-65 | Prefer not to answer
- 4) What is your highest level of education?
 - Less than a high school degree | High school degree or equivalent [Non-university education beyond high-school (technical college, community college, vocational education) | Some college, no degree | Bachelor's or Associate's degree | Master's degree | Doctoral degree | Prefer not to answer
- 5) Are you a practitioner (researcher, working professional) in Artificial Intelligence?
 - Yes | No | Prefer not to answer
- 6) Please provide your Prolific ID, this is important to get the compensation.